

Studies on the Reaction of Iron Sulphide with Butan-1-ol in the Vapour Phase

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A new reaction of iron sulphide with butan-1-ol in the vapour phase a 359–500° producing mainly 1,1'-thiobis(butane) and 1,1-dibutoxybutane is reported. Iron sulphide (FeS) catalyses the formation of 1,1-dibutoxybutane and decomposition of 1-butane thiol.

As a part of the overall scheme of preparation of organosulphur compounds by the reaction of iron pyrite with alcohols^{1,2}, the reaction of iron sulphide (FeS₂) with butan-1-ol in the vapour phase has been carried out in a fixed bed flow-reactor at 350–500°. A new reaction of potential industrial application for preparation of 1,1'-thiobis(butane) and 1,1-dibutoxybutane and the catalytic role of iron sulphides (FeS₂ and FeS) are reported.

Results and Discussion

The elimination of sulphur from iron sulphide and the product distribution were studied under different conditions of the following process variables. The range of process variables were : particle size (–85 + 200 B.S.S.), temperature (350–500°), partial pressure of alcohol vapour (0.1–1.0 atm), reaction period (15–60 min) and contact time (0.014–0.066 s). The extent of sulphur eliminated from synthetic iron sulphide as hydrogen sulphide, 1,1'-thiobis(butane) and 1-butane thiol at three different temperatures is given in Table 1. The liquid product distribution as obtained by gas chromatography under similar conditions is given in Table 2. It is observed that the yields of 1,1-dibutoxybutane, 1,1'-thiobis(butane) and 1-butane thiol increase with temperature.

TABLE 1—SULPHUR ELIMINATION AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES*

Temp. °C	Sulphur eliminated %	Sulphur eliminated as (%)		
		Hydrogen sulphide	1,1'-Thiobis- (butane)	1-butane- thiol
350	25.40	0.5	20.75	1.35
450	44.35	3.5	38.30	0.60
500	49.50	4.7	41.70	0.55

*Particle size, –150 + 200 BSS; partial pressure of alcohol, 1 atm; reaction period, 60 min; contact time, 0.066 s.

TABLE 2—LIQUID PRODUCT DISTRIBUTION AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES IN SYNTHETIC IRON SULPHIDE*

Temp. °C	Product distribution (vol %)				
	1,1-Dibutoxy- butane	1-Butane- thiol	1,1-Thio- bis(butane)	Butan-1-ol	Butanal
350	7.69	1.95	0.02	85.6	2.65
450	17.75	0.00	0.04	75.2	2.86
500	18.80	0.17	4.70	68.0	6.60

*Particle size, –150 + 200 BSS; partial pressure of alcohol, 1 atm; reaction period, 60 min; contact time, 0.066 s.

Under conditions (Table 1), at 500° 33.3% of sulphur was eliminated from natural iron pyrite. A typical gas chromatogram of the liquid products produced in the reaction of pure butan-1-ol with synthetic iron sulphide at 500° for 60 min showed the presence of 18.8% 1,1-dibutoxybutane, 4.7% 1,1'-thiobis(butane), 6.6% butanal, 68% unconverted butan-1-ol and small quantities of 1-butane thiol, 1,1'-oxybis(butane) and ten other compounds. The solid product

contained FeS along with small quantities of Fe₂O₃ and unreacted FeS₂. Sulphur elimination was enhanced to a small extent by ferric oxide and aluminium oxide and retarded by calcium oxide, thoria and silica.

1,1'-Thiobis(butane) could be formed by the direct reaction,

or through the intermediate formation of butane thiol,

Formation of water and oxygen indicates that the reaction proceeds by both these schemes. Formation of 1,1'-thiobis(butane) and sulphur elimination increase greatly with increase in the partial pressure of alcohol (Table 3). This supports reaction (3). The liquid product distribution at three partial pressures as obtained by gas chromatography is given in Table 4.

TABLE 3—SULPHUR ELIMINATION AT DIFFERENT PARTIAL PRESSURES OF ALCOHOL*

Partial pressure of alcohol atm	Sulphur eliminated %	Sulphur eliminated as (%)		
		Hydrogen sulphide	1,1'-Thiobis-(butane)	1-butane-thiol
0.17	28.21	1.94	16.14	0.13
1.31	30.03	2.50	25.55	0.45
1.00	44.35	3.50	38.30	0.60

* Particle size, -150 + 200 BSS; temperature, 500°; reaction period, 60 min; contact time, 0.066 s.

TABLE 4—LIQUID PRODUCT DISTRIBUTION AT DIFFERENT PARTIAL PRESSURES OF ALCOHOL*

Partial pressure atm	Product distribution (vol %)				
	1,1-Dibutoxy-butane	1-Butane-thiol	1,1'-Thiobis-(butane)	Butan-1-ol	Butanal
0.17	6.15	0.13	0.02	93.0	0.44
0.31	9.63	0.18	0.03	88.0	1.00
1.00	7.70	1.95	0.02	85.6	2.65

* Particle size, -150 + 200 BSS; temperature, 350°; reaction period, 60 min; contact time, 0.066 s.

The present study indicates that the decomposition of 1-butane thiol to 1,1'-thiobis(butane) is catalysed by iron sulphides. The preparation of alkyl sulphides by decomposition of mercaptans over ZnS/CdS catalyst has been reported³. Gas chromatogram of products at different temperatures indicate that the relative proportion of 1,1'-thiobis(butane) increases while that of 1-butane thiol decreases with temperature. This supports reaction (3). Direct formation of 1-butane thiol by reaction of hydrogen sulphide and alcohol over iron sulphide (FeS₂) was negligible. There was no reaction of FeS and butan-1-ol upto 500°.

The unique feature of this study was the formation of 1,1-dibutoxybutane. 1,1-Dibutoxybutane is used as a organic solvent, starting material for perfumes, essences and agrochemicals. Its only method of manufacture is patented⁴. It is probable that butan-1-ol undergoes dehydrogenation to give butanal (reaction 4) and this reacts with butan-1-ol to produce 1,1-dibutoxybutane by acetal formation (reaction 5),

The study confirms that both these reactions are catalysed by iron sulphides (FeS₂, FeS). It was further confirmed that 1,1-dibutoxybutane was not formed by the thermal decomposition of butan-1-ol.

The yield of butanal and 1,1-dibutoxybutane under different conditions are given in Table 5. The reaction of iron sulphide (FeS₂) with butan-1-ol at 500° for 60 min and 1.0 atm. partial pressure of alcohol produced 6.6% butanal and 18.8% 1,1-dibutoxybutane. Under exactly

similar condition, the reaction of FeS with butan-1-ol produced 1.1% butanal and 17.7% 1,1-dibutoxybutane. The study indicates that FeS₂ is a better dehydrogenating catalyst (reaction 4) and FeS is a better dehydration catalyst (reaction 5).

TABLE 5—YIELD OF PRODUCTS UNDER DIFFERENT CONDITIONS*

Reaction conditions	Yield of products (vol %)	
	Butanal	1,1-Dibutoxybutane
Vapour of butan-1-ol over a bed of FeS ₂	6.60	18.80
Vapour of butan-1-ol over a bed of FeS	1.14	17.70
Vapour of butan-1-ol over a bed of FeS ₂ (50%) and FeS (50%)	1.40	19.10

*Temperature, 500°; reaction period, 60 min; partial pressure of alcohol, 1 atm; contact time, 0.066 s.

In order to ascertain the catalytic role of FeS₂ and FeS on the formation of 1,1-dibutoxybutane, the reaction of butan-1-ol with butanal was carried out at 500° in the vapour phase in a fixed bed flow reactor. The results are given in Table 6. The yield of 1,1-dibutoxybutane increases substantially both in the presence of FeS₂ and FeS. The reaction of butan-1-ol with FeS₂ produces FeS. Therefore, it could be inferred that the effective catalyst for the acetal formation (1,1-dibutoxybutane) is FeS. Detailed studies on the mechanism and kinetics of the reaction are in progress.

TABLE 6—REACTION OF BUTAN-1-OL WITH BUTANAL*

Catalyst	Yield of 1,1-dibutoxybutane (vol. %)
Non-catalytic	26.1
FeS ₂	42.5
FeS	59.1

*Particle size, -50 + 200 BSS; partial pressure of alcohol, 0.63 atm; reaction period, 30 min; contact time, 0.066 s, temperature, 500°.

Experimental

The apparatus for the reaction of iron sulphide with butan-1-ol consisted of an arrangement for feeding the gaseous reactants, a reactor and an arrangement for condensing and absorbing the gases/vapours. Nitrogen from the cylinder

was purified and dried and then metered through a calibrated flow meter. Butyl alcohol was allowed to fall into the evaporator at the desired flow rate by using a high precision peristaltic pump. The evaporator consisted of a thermometer pocket, an inlet for butanol, another inlet for nitrogen gas and an outlet for butanol vapour and nitrogen gas. The evaporator was heated on a heating mantle whose temperature was controlled by a Sunvic energy regulator. The outlet of the evaporator connected to the tubular reactor was wrapped by heating tape to prevent cooling. The pre-heating portion of the tubular glass reactor (1 inch dia × 12 inch) was packed with glass beads and glass wool. The bed of iron sulphide was fixed at the center of the reactor by packing with glass wool. The reactor was heated in a temperature controlled tubular furnace of precision ± 1°. The vapours/gases were condensed by a water-cooled condenser and collected in receivers. The uncondensed gases were collected in a series of absorbers.

Iron sulphide (1–2 g) was fed into the reactor after the glass bead packing. The evaporator and the reactor was preheated in an atmosphere of nitrogen. When the desired temperature was attained, the flow of nitrogen was stopped and butanol was passed through the system at the desired flow rate for a definite reaction time. After the reaction period, heating and butanol vapour supply were stopped and nitrogen gas was passed through the system to remove the residual gases, which were condensed and collected. The condensed products were estimated for alkyl mercaptan and alkyl sulphide by the reported method⁵. The uncondensed vapours/gases were absorbed in a series of absorbers. Formaldehyde was absorbed in water, hydrogen sulphide was absorbed in 0.1 N cadmium acetate solution and the unsaturated gases were passed through a solution of iodine monochloride. The reactor was cooled to room temperature and the solid residue was estimated for total residual sulphur by the reported method⁶.

The natural iron sulphide was supplied by the Ingaldah Mines located at Chitradurga, Karnataka, India. The composition of the ore with particle size $-150 + 200$ B.S.S. was 79.10% FeS_2 (Fe, 38.39; S, 42.4; SiO_2 , 18; other impurities, 1%). Synthetic iron sulphide was prepared by passing hydrogen sulphide over about 15 g of ferric oxide heated at $400-425^\circ$ for 1 h⁷. The purified and dried synthetic iron sulphide contained 99.02% FeS_2 (Fe, 46.14; S, 52.88%). The purity of the sample was further confirmed by X-ray diffraction. The butan-1-ol, additives and other chemicals used were of analytical grade.

The total reaction product of n-butanol was subjected to detailed gas chromatographic analysis to find out the number of products formed and the product distribution under different reaction conditions using a Shimadzu 15A instrument : column used SE 30, the injection port temperature 220° and detection temperature 250° . The sample was heated from 60 to 200° at the rate of $8^\circ/\text{min}$. The flow rate of the carrier gas was 40 ml h^{-1} .

The total reaction product gave a positive test for thiols, sulphides, aldehydes, polysulphides, alcohols and unsaturation, thus indicating the presence of a mixture of compounds. This was subjected to distillation at atmospheric pressure and fractions at different boiling point ranges were collected : (i) fraction-I ($74-86^\circ$), (ii) fraction-II ($95-110^\circ$), (iii) fraction-III ($115-118^\circ$) and (iv) fraction-IV (did not distill but decomposed on heating beyond 140°). Fraction-I was found to contain mainly butanal, fraction-II 1-butanethiol, fraction-III unreacted butan-1-ol and fraction-IV 1,1-dibutoxybutane and 1,1'-thiobis(butane). The products present in the first three fractions were identified by chemical methods and gas chromatography-mass spectra (GCMS). 1,1-Dibutoxybutane was identified as follows : Fraction-IV was subjected to column chromatography on a alumina column and a mixture of hexane-benzene (1 : 1) was used as eluent. The different fractions collected were subjected to gas chromatography.

1,1-Dibutoxybutane obtained had a purity of 95.8%. It was found to distill at $83-85^\circ$ under 3 mm Hg pressure. The structure was confirmed by detailed spectroscopic analysis. The nmr and ^{13}C nmr spectra of the sample was carried out on a Bruker AMX-360 MHz instrument. This confirmed the presence of four different kinds of hydrogen environments in the molecule and the presence of eight magnetically non-equivalent carbon atoms respectively. The infrared spectra (Perkin-Elmer) indicated the presence of acetal linkage and the mass spectra (Hewlett-Packard 5890) confirmed the structure of 1,1-dibutoxybutane. 1,1'-Thiobis(butane) was confirmed by chemical and GCMS method.

The uncondensed gaseous products contained hydrogen sulphide and small quantities of water, carbon monoxide, oxygen and saturated and unsaturated hydrocarbons. The mass balance for each run with respect to iron and sulphur was done and only such results were accepted where the mass balance was at least 99%.

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